

**The Knowledge Café as a Case Method in Synchronous Online Classroom – "The
OD Consultant at Animens" Case Study**

Robert M Yawson, PhD

Department of Entrepreneurship, International Business & Strategy, School of Business,
Quinnipiac University, CT, USA

Emmanuel Osafo, PhD

WSU-Extension | Benton-Franklin Counties, Washington State University, WA, USA

Obi Damoah Berko, PhD

Department of Organization and Human Resource Management, University of Ghana
Business School, Legon, Ghana

Lily Yarney, PhD

Department of Public Administration and Health Services Management, University of
Ghana Business School, Legon, Ghana

23rd - 26th of July, 2023

University of St. Andrews, Scotland, United Kingdom

Copyright ©2023 Yawson, Osafo, Berko & Yarney

Abstract

The Knowledge Cafe Approach is a participatory and collaborative method for group dialogue and idea exchange. It is a valuable pedagogical tool in management education, providing a structured and engaging way for students to share and explore ideas and perspectives on complex management issues. We developed the Knowledge Café approach as an alternative to the World Café approach for synchronous online classroom use. Using a case study, we illustrate how the Knowledge Café can be used as a Case Method in a synchronous online classroom. Animens Industries Ltd is located in the port city of Takoradi in Ghana. It was established in 1972 as the first wholly Ghanaian-owned distilleries and bottling company. The Animens Case Study was developed to serve as a universal case study but specifically to students in Africa and Ghana especially. Students generally respond positively to the Knowledge Café exercise, as it provides a structured and engaging way to share ideas, collaborate with peers, and learn from one another. Students often find the activity a valuable learning experience that helps them develop critical thinking, communication, and collaboration skills.

Introduction.

The World Cafe approach is an innovative pedagogical tool facilitating large-scale group discussions in a participatory and collaborative environment. The approach has been utilized as an effective tool for management education, offering students an opportunity to engage in dialogue, share knowledge and ideas, and engage in collaborative problem-solving (Yawson et al., 2019).

According to Brown and Isaacs (2005), the World Cafe approach encourages collaborative conversations and fosters collective intelligence. The approach is built on dialogue, participation, and collective intelligence principles. Through this approach, participants engage in open, respectful dialogue, sharing their ideas and perspectives, learning from each other, and co-creating new knowledge (Brown & Isaacs, 2005). The approach is designed to be interactive and engaging, allowing participants to work together to develop solutions to complex problems.

However, its use in synchronous online classrooms has been a challenge. At the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, universities with the needed infrastructure moved all their classes online, and the lead author of this paper developed the Knowledge Café as an adaptation of the World Café for synchronous online classrooms.

This exercise aims to illustrate how to use the Knowledge Café. The Knowledge Café exercise can be used in early undergraduate, late undergraduate, graduate, etc.; traditional, non-traditional, cross-cultural, etc., classroom settings. As added objective to this manuscript, we decided to use the Animens case study to demonstrate the use of the knowledge café in this exercise because of its indigeneity. The case method and business cases are widely used in business schools worldwide as effective teaching tools that provide students with real-world examples and opportunities to apply theoretical concepts to practical situations (Nohria, 2021). However, using business cases in business schools in Africa can be challenging due to several factors. Key among them is the relevance of cases to local needs: Many business cases used in business schools worldwide are based on companies and industries in North America, Europe, and Asia, which might be *alien* to the African student with no experience in this regard. Therefore, African students may find it difficult to relate to the business contexts presented in these cases, as the African business environment is often very different. This makes it essential to develop business

cases relevant to the African context and showcase African companies and industries. The Animens case study does just that.

Theoretical Foundation/Teaching Implications.

The Knowledge Cafe Approach is a participatory and collaborative method for group dialogue and idea exchange. It can be a valuable pedagogical tool in management education, as it provides a structured and engaging way for students to share and explore ideas and perspectives on complex management issues. The theoretical foundation and teaching implications of using the Knowledge Cafe Approach in management education include:

1. **Constructivist learning theory:** The Knowledge Cafe Approach is grounded in constructivist learning theory, which suggests that learning occurs through the active construction of knowledge by the learner (Archambault et al., 2022). In the Knowledge Cafe, students actively engage in dialogue, sharing their own experiences and perspectives, and building on the ideas of others. This allows them to construct new knowledge and meaning through the process of dialogue and collaboration.
2. **Experiential learning:** The Knowledge Café Approach emphasizes experiential learning, which is a powerful way to engage students and help them internalize new knowledge (Heinrich & Green, 2020). By actively participating in the Knowledge Café, students have the opportunity to apply their theoretical knowledge to real-world management challenges and to learn from the experiences and perspectives of their peers.
3. **Social learning:** The Knowledge Café Approach fosters social learning, which is the process of learning through social interaction and collaboration with others (Khechine et al., 2020). By creating a collaborative and supportive learning environment, the Knowledge Café allows students to share their perspectives, build on the ideas of others, and learn from one another.
4. **Critical thinking:** The Knowledge Café Approach encourages critical thinking, which is a key skill for effective management. By engaging in dialogue and exchanging ideas, students can develop critical thinking skills, learn to evaluate

information and arguments and develop their own perspectives on complex management issues (García-Carrión et al., 2020).

5. **Communication skills:** The Knowledge Cafe Approach can help students develop effective written and oral communication skills essential for successful management. By participating in group dialogue and sharing their ideas, students can develop their ability to articulate their thoughts clearly and effectively, listen actively to others, and engage in constructive dialogue (Kelly, 2018).

Learning Objectives.

Learning objectives for using a Knowledge Café approach for an Organizational Behavior case study analysis could include:

1. Improved knowledge and understanding of the case study topic: Through sharing diverse perspectives and exchanging ideas in a Knowledge Café approach, participants can gain a more comprehensive understanding of the case study topic.
2. Enhanced critical thinking skills: Participants can develop their critical thinking skills as they engage in discussions and consider different perspectives, opinions, and ideas shared by others.
3. Increased creativity and innovation: The Knowledge Café approach can help stimulate creativity and innovation by encouraging participants to think outside the box and generate novel solutions to the problems or challenges presented in the case study.
4. Improved communication and collaboration skills: The Knowledge Café approach can help develop effective communication and collaboration skills as participants work together to share ideas and insights and engage in productive discussions.
5. Heightened awareness of diversity and inclusion: By facilitating a space where everyone's voice is heard and respected, the Knowledge Café approach can help promote diversity and inclusion and foster an environment where all participants feel valued and included.
6. Greater self-awareness and personal growth: Through participating in the Knowledge Café approach, participants can develop a greater awareness of their own thoughts, beliefs, and biases, and challenge their assumptions, leading to personal growth and development.

Exercise Overview.

The following is an overview of the logistics, flow, variations, and debriefing guidelines for running the Knowledge Cafe exercise in a synchronous online classroom.

Logistics:

- **Class size:** Ideally, the exercise should be conducted with a group of 12-25 students. However, it can be adapted to larger or smaller groups.
- **Materials:** Any Device with internet access and spreadsheet processing capabilities (obviously, for an online class, everyone is on the internet).
- **Timing:** The exercise can be conducted in 30 minutes to 2 hours, depending on the complexity of the topic and the depth of the discussion, and the class size.

Flow of the exercise:

1. Introduce the case and provide some background information to the students.
2. Breakout Room is created on Zoom, Google Meet, or the appropriate video conferencing software.
3. Randomly assign students. Ideally, each breakout room will be 4 – 6 people.
4. Provide the students with a set amount of time (usually 20-30 minutes) to discuss the assigned question, generate ideas and insights, and write it down on the Google/DropBox/OneDrive Spread Sheet.
5. After the first round of discussion, each room will comment, analyze or critique the initial inputs of the other rooms. The new group reviews the key ideas and insights generated by the original room and builds on them by generating new insights and ideas.
6. Reconvene as a large group and have a debriefing session.

Debriefing guidelines specifically for the Animens case:

1. What are the advantages and disadvantages of family businesses? How can family businesses effectively manage conflicts that arise when restructuring?
2. What role do consultants play in organizational restructuring? Do you think the OD Consultant in the Animens restructuring was effective?
3. What would you have done differently if you were the OD Consultant?

Session Description.

Knowledge Café – "The OD Consultant at Animens" Case Study

- **Each Breakout RM is Assigned a corresponding Case Question as follows:**
 1. What are the advantages and disadvantages of family businesses? How can family businesses effectively manage conflicts that arise when restructuring?
 2. What role do consultants play in organizational restructuring? Do you think the OD Consultant in the Animens restructuring was effective?
 3. What would you have done differently if you were the OD Consultant?
- Each room will provide four key discussion pts from the question assigned in Column 1.
- Each RM will then visit the Excel Sheet tab of each Breakout Room and critique/reflect/provide comments in the respective column.
- https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1jCd9iguRzNi3i4U084xRjrSSeOYgD86hp3_SzU8VHsk/edit?usp=sharing
- After the Groups are recalled into the main room, each breakout room reports the summary of the discussions and comments to the class for overall discussions.

Appendices.

Attached as an Appendix is the Animens Case Study

References

- Archambault, L., Leary, H., & Rice, K. (2022). Pillars of online pedagogy: A framework for teaching in online learning environments. *Educational Psychologist, 57*(3), 178–191. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2022.2051513>
- Brown, J., & Isaacs, D. (2005). *The World Café: Shaping Our Futures Through Conversations That Matter* (Illustrate). Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
- García-Carrión, R., López de Aguilera, G., Padrós, M., & Ramis-Salas, M. (2020). Implications for Social Impact of Dialogic Teaching and Learning. *Frontiers in Psychology, 11*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00140>
- Heinrich, W. F., & Green, P. M. (2020). Remixing Approaches to Experiential Learning, Design, and Assessment. *Journal of Experiential Education, 43*(2), 205–223. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1053825920915608>
- Kelly, A. (2018). *Social Skills*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315173405>
- Khechine, H., Raymond, B., & Augier, M. (2020). The adoption of a social learning system: Intrinsic value in the UTAUT model. *British Journal of Educational Technology, 51*(6), 2306–2325. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12905>
- Nohria, N. (2021, December). What the Case Study Method Really Teaches. *Harvard Business Review Education, 8*. <https://hbr.org/2021/12/what-the-case-study-method-really-teaches>
- Yawson, R. M., Sprinkle, T. A., Urick, M., & Johnson-Kanda, I. (2019). Using the World Café Approach for Class Discussion Participation and Engagement. *"Teaching Agents for Positive Change" Proceedings of MOBTS 2019 Conference*, 1–8.

Appendix

Abbreviated Version of "The OD Consultant at Animens" Case Study

History of company

Animens Industries Ltd is located in the port city of Takoradi in Ghana. It was established in 1972 as the first wholly Ghanaian-owned distilleries and bottling company. The company was established by a lady entrepreneur - Anita Mensah. A lady with no formal education but has had an apprenticeship at a cottage distillery. Her dreams of expanding her cottage industry led to the company Animens.

As of December 1998, Animens had over 170 employees, branches in three other countries in the West African Sub-Region, and in addition to the Beverage and Bottling Industry, had ventured into the Hotel Industry and Mining Equipment Supply Industry. In the early 1990s, Animens became a very profitable industry and acquired government loans to expand the business.

Organizational structure

Case Exhibit 1: *Organizational Structure of Animens Industries before restructuring*

The chairperson was the sole proprietor of the company. As a family business, the Managing Director was the son of the chairperson. The rest of the employees are not necessarily relatives of the owner of the company.

The company's fortunes began to decline as they started facing fierce competition in beverage and bottling industries and as a result of wrangling and power struggle within the family for the company's control.

In line with the Government of Ghana's policy of helping local industries survive global competition, a scheme called a Business Assistance Fund (BAF) was set up where struggling local companies can apply for capital to revitalize their businesses. As part of the capital is a condition that the company will hire a consultant approved by the BAF secretariat to assist the company in restructuring.

Animens opted for the BAF and hired a well-known advertising mogul as the Organization Development (OD) consultant. The consultant, in agreement with the Board of the company, started reorganizing the company. He first abolished the position of the Managing Director, with the reason that it was a replication of duties, and that the chairperson was doing almost the same job. He recommended the MD, the son of the chairperson, to be the General Manager responsible for the Mining supplies operations of the company where he had the expertise. The Manager for the hotel was reassigned during the restructuring process, and a new person was hired.

Case Exhibit 2: *New Organizational Structure of Animens Industries*

A new position was created, which looked like the former role of the Managing Director, but with a new name as Group General Manager (GGM). This new GGM was a recent graduate with a first degree in Chemistry and a Master's in Biochemistry, and two

years of experience with a multinational as a Quality Control Officer. Another key hire was the Finance and Administration Manager (FAM), a Chartered Accountant (CA) with over five years of practice in Southern Africa. The new organizational structure thus looked like as shown in Exhibit 2.

That ended the official role of the OD consultant leaving behind an elaborate report and recommendations. The GGM, with little administrative experience, relied heavily on the F&A manager, who had a lot of experience. At the first management meeting, the GM of mining supplies indirectly made it clear that he was not too happy with the new organizational structure and that no one should expect him to be taking any unnecessary instructions. The meeting ended with a list of things to do based on the ODs report and inputs received from three staff durbars held at the three main branches of the company.

The priority areas were:

1. Addressing inefficiencies in the system leading to financial waste
2. Restructuring of purchasing and supply practices
3. Refocusing Cooperate Social Responsibility (CSR)
4. Tackle salary disparities
5. Reopening and closing of some sales depot
6. Staff re-alignment

Addressing inefficiencies

The first recommendation the GGM and FAM made was to the chairperson to reduce the monthly meeting of the management board from monthly to 3 times a year. - every four months. The Board was made up of two other sons of the chairperson, an attorney for the company (who was not on a company pay role), a Member of Parliament (MP) for the constituency where the company is located, and two other people with Anita Mensah as the chairperson. Although the chairperson and the attorney were in favor of this recommendation, it did not go down well with the rest of the members, especially the two sons who thought some "foreigners" wanted to take over the company that they had built with their "sweat and blood" and vowed to resist any attempt by any group of persons to hijack the company.

The chairperson operated from 3 allocated offices, one at the hotel, one at the industry, and one at the mining supplies. It was recommended that she should operate only from the corporate head office. It did not go down well with her.

Restructuring purchasing and supply

Prior to the restructuring, the MD, the son who is now the Head of mining supplies, was in charge of purchasing and supply. However, the GGM recommended that this responsibility be given to the FAM with the expertise. This created another serious conflict.

Refocusing Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

It was realized that what was referred to as CSR mainly was going to finance the campaign of the board member, and this was also stopped immediately, which pitched the GGM directly against the MP, who vowed to make sure that the GGM was removed.

Salary disparities

It was realized that there were serious salary disparities, with the workers at the distillery being the lowest paid, although they generated the highest profit. Salaries were streamlined across Board by raising the wages of those disadvantaged.

Reopening and closing of the depots

The company's had sales depots scattered around the entire country. The nonperforming ones were recommended for closing, and new ones were opened, especially in neighboring countries – Togo, Cote d'Ivoire, and Burkina Faso.

Staff re-alignment

A deliberate effort was made to realign staff.

Conclusion

All these changes were made within three months of taking over the positions by the GGM and the FAM. However, clear significant progress was made with the company making a profit from the 4th month onwards. The day-to-day interference by the chairperson and the constant interference and instructions issued to employees and line managers by the board members became very intense.

A year after taking over, the GGM resigned, and the FAM resigned three months later. Three years after the resignations, the Bottling and Distillery was closed down.